

Deliverable D3.1

Open Access Policy

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Name	Details of contribution
Stavros Iezekiel	Author and responsible for revision of the document

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1 Introduction and Objectives

The University of Cyprus currently does not maintain a formally approved Open Access Policy for research infrastructures. This document establishes the framework governing access to the research infrastructure developed under the ALPHA project, funded through the OPEN INFRA/0625 call.

The primary objective of the ALPHA project is to ensure the optimal utilisation of the infrastructure by both internal and external stakeholders. Through this framework, the project aims to support research excellence, foster collaboration, and drive innovation across academia, industry, and society.

Access will be provided in a transparent, fair, and non-discriminatory manner, in alignment with national and European Union regulations, including compliance with the “Do No Significant Harm” principle, General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), and applicable state aid rules.

This document constitutes Deliverable D3.1 of the ALPHA project and defines the Open Access Policy governing the use of the research infrastructure. It is accompanied by the associated Pricing Policy, while proof of registration in the National Research Infrastructure Platform (<https://cri.gov.cy>) is provided in Deliverable D2.4. The policy reflects the current operational framework and may be subject to updates in line with institutional, national, and European requirements.

2 Users and Access Allocation

2.1 Categories of Users

Access to the infrastructure will be granted to:

- Internal Users: Academic and research staff of the University of Cyprus
- External Academic Users: Researchers from national and international universities and public research organisations
- External Non-Academic Users: Enterprises (including SMEs and start-ups), governmental authorities, NGOs, and civil society stakeholders (quadruple helix model)

2.2 Indicative Allocation of Access Time

- Internal Users: 50%
- External Academic Users: 30%
- External Non-Academic / Industry Users: 20%

These allocations may be adjusted based on demand, strategic priorities, and infrastructure availability, while maintaining alignment with the principles of open and equitable access.

3 Available Equipment

The ALPHA research infrastructure provides advanced capabilities in RF, microwave, millimetre-wave, and optical systems through the following equipment:

- **Rohde & Schwarz SMA100B Signal Generator (up to 67 GHz)**

- Featuring low phase noise and high output power options.
- **Keysight N5227B PNA Network Analyzer**
Equipped with spectrum analysis functionality up to 70 GHz (S930907B option).
- **Zepren BOSA Series 6 Optical Spectrum Analyzer (C+L Band)**
Includes laser output, component analysis, and phase measurement capabilities.
- **Thorlabs MX70G Calibrated Electro-Optical Converter**
Incorporates automatic bias control, RF operation up to 67 GHz, and an integrated C-band laser.

4 Access Framework and Legal Instruments

Access to the ALPHA infrastructure follows the model established by the European Commission Joint Research Centre (JRC):

4.1 Relevance-Driven Access

Access is granted based on scientific excellence or societal relevance. It is typically offered free of charge or at subsidised rates for publicly funded, non-commercial research aligned with national research and innovation priorities.

4.2 Market-Driven Access

Commercial access is offered to private-sector users. Services are provided at full cost, with discounted rates available for micro and small SMEs, in compliance with state aid regulations.

4.3 Legal Agreements

Access is governed through two legal instruments:

- **Research Infrastructure Access Agreement (RIAA)**

Signed between the host organisation and the external user institution, defining scope, duration, responsibilities, and legal conditions.

- **User Access Agreement (UAA)**

Signed by individual users, covering:

- Intellectual property rights
- Data protection and confidentiality
- Liability and insurance
- Health and safety procedures
- Code of conduct

Templates for these agreements are included as Annexes A and B at the end of the present document.

5 Pricing Policy

A transparent pricing model is implemented, with rates expressed in **EUR per hour per instrument**:

Service	External Academic Rates (€)	Micro- and Small-SME Rates (€)	Non-SME Rates (€)
Training	50	100	150
Use of Instrument	20	50	100
Staff Assistance	20	50	100

- **Internal Academic Users** (i.e. researchers from the University of Cyprus) may be granted access free of charge, but subject to internal institutional policies and resource availability.
- **External Academic Rates** apply to researchers from institutions **outside the University of Cyprus** conducting publicly funded, non-commercial research.
- **Micro- and Small-SME Rates** apply exclusively to enterprises that qualify as **micro or small SMEs** (i.e. fewer than 50 employees and annual turnover or balance sheet total below €10 million), in accordance with EU definitions.
- **Non-SME Rates** apply to:
 - Medium-sized enterprises
 - Large companies
 - Other commercial users operating on a market-driven basis

Pricing is determined based on operational costs, technical support requirements, and market benchmarking.

The pricing scheme and access conditions are subject to periodic review and adjustment. Updates may occur due to equipment ageing and maintenance needs, evolving operational costs, user demand, stakeholder feedback, and updates to policies of the University of Cyprus or relevant national and European frameworks.

6 Access Application and Evaluation Procedure

Access is granted through a structured process:

- **Submission:** Completion of an online Access Request Form via the infrastructure portal (<https://cri.gov.cy/gr/mitrwo-ereynitikwn-ypodomwn/engineering-and-energy/electrical-and-optical-engineering-facilities/advanced-laboratory-for-photonics-and-high-frequency-applications-alpha>)
- **Evaluation Criteria:**
 - Scientific and/or technological merit
 - Technical feasibility and availability
 - Compliance with safety and ethical standards
 - User expertise

- **Scheduling:** Allocation of access time based on demand and availability
- **Contractualisation:** Signing of required agreements prior to access

All access activities are monitored and recorded to ensure transparency and accountability.

7 Intellectual Property and Exploitation of Results

Intellectual property generated by external users remains the property of the user and/or their institution unless otherwise specified in the agreements.

Jointly generated intellectual property will be governed by the policies of the University of Cyprus.

Users are encouraged to collaborate with the RIF Central Knowledge Transfer Office (CKTO) to develop appropriate exploitation strategies aligned with national innovation priorities.

8 Data Protection and Confidentiality

All data will be managed in accordance with:

- General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)
- Internal policies of the University of Cyprus

Key safeguards include:

- Confidentiality clauses in agreements
- Secure storage and access control systems
- Logging and traceability of data usage

Users must explicitly accept these conditions prior to access.

9 Promotion and Awareness

To ensure visibility and utilisation of the infrastructure:

- Open calls and expressions of interest will be launched
- A dedicated webpage will provide access information, scheduling, and documentation
- Training sessions, workshops, and outreach activities will be organised
- Participation in national and European research networks will be pursued

Users must acknowledge the use of the ALPHA infrastructure in all resulting outputs (publications, patents, datasets, etc.).

10 Governance and Sustainability

Access to the ALPHA research infrastructure is managed and overseen by the **Scientific Responsible**, Stavros Iezekiel, Professor at the University of Cyprus.

The Scientific Responsible is accountable for:

- Reviewing and approving access applications
- Monitoring infrastructure usage and performance
- Ensuring compliance with access policies and applicable regulations
- Addressing user-related issues and operational matters
- Recommending updates to the Open Access Policy when necessary

The Scientific Responsible may be supported by technical staff where required for operational, safety, and maintenance aspects.

The infrastructure will remain operational for at least **five (5) years** after project completion, supported by institutional funding and integration into national and European research infrastructure networks.

11 Integration into the National Infrastructure Framework

The ALPHA infrastructure will:

- **Be maintained in full operational condition**
- **Undergo annual evaluation** regarding scientific relevance, impact, and access quality

Annex A – Research Infrastructure Access Agreement (RIAA)

A.1 Parties

Host Organisation	University of Cyprus
User Institution	
Address	
Contact Person	

A.2 Subject and Scope of the Agreement

This Agreement defines the terms and conditions under which the User Institution is granted access to the ALPHA research infrastructure of the University of Cyprus.

It specifies:

- The scope and nature of the activities to be carried out
- The infrastructure, equipment, and services to be accessed
- The applicable access mode (relevance-driven or market-driven)
- The rights and obligations of the Parties

Access is granted exclusively for the activities described in Section A.3. Any use beyond the agreed scope requires prior written approval from the Host Organisation.

A.3 Scope of Access

Project Title	
Description of Project Activities	
Equipment / Services Requested	
Access Period [Start Date – End Date]	
Access Type	<input type="checkbox"/> Non-commercial <input type="checkbox"/> Commercial

A.4 Responsibilities of the Parties

Host Organisation

- Provide access to the agreed infrastructure and technical support
- Ensure safe and operational conditions
- Provide necessary training and guidance where applicable

User Institution

- Use infrastructure only within the agreed scope
- Ensure personnel are appropriately qualified and trained
- Comply with all safety, ethical, and legal requirements
- Ensure proper handling of equipment

A.5 Access Conditions and Fees

Pricing Category	[Academic / Micro-Small SME / Non-SME]
Estimated Cost (€)	
Payment Terms	

A.6 Intellectual Property Rights (IPR)

- Intellectual property generated solely by the User remains the property of the User
- Jointly generated results shall be governed by the policies of the University of Cyprus
- Specific provisions (if applicable):

A.7 Confidentiality

Both parties agree to maintain confidentiality of all non-public information exchanged during the project.

A.8 Data Protection

All personal data shall be processed in accordance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and applicable institutional policies.

A.9 Liability and Insurance

- The User Institution is responsible for damages caused by its personnel due to negligence or misuse
- The Host Organisation shall not be liable for indirect or consequential damages
- The User Institution may be required to provide proof of insurance

A.10 Health and Safety

Users must comply with all safety procedures and training requirements prior to access.

A.11 Duration and Termination

- This Agreement is valid for the duration specified in Section A.3
- Either party may terminate the Agreement with written notice in case of breach or justified reasons

A.12 Governing Law

This Agreement is governed by the laws of the Republic of Cyprus.

A.13 Signatures

Host Organisation Representative	
Name	
Function/Title	
Signature	
Date	
User Institution Representative	
Name	
Function/Title	
Signature	
Date	

Annex B – User Access Agreement (UAA)

B.1 User Information

Full Name	
Affiliation	
Contact Details	

B.2 Approved Use of Infrastructure

Description of Work (DoW) by the User	
Equipment to be Used by the User	

The User agrees to use the infrastructure strictly within the approved scope defined in the corresponding RIAA.

Any modification to the approved Description of Work requires prior written approval from the University of Cyprus.

Use of the infrastructure outside the approved scope is strictly prohibited.

B.3 User Obligations

The User shall:

- Use the infrastructure only for approved purposes
- Follow all operational and safety procedures
- Respect staff and other users
- Avoid misuse or damage

B.4 Intellectual Property

- The User retains rights to independently generated results
- Joint results are governed by University of Cyprus policies
- Specific provisions (if applicable):

B.5 Data Protection and Confidentiality

The User agrees to comply with:

- General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)
- Confidential handling of information

B.6 Health and Safety Compliance

Requirement	Confirmation
Safety training completed and understood	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No

B.7 Liability

The User is responsible for:

- Damage caused due to negligence
- Proper use of equipment

B.8 Code of Conduct

Users must:

- Act professionally and ethically at all times
- Follow all instructions
- Respect institutional rules
- Ensure a safe and collaborative working environment

B.9 Acknowledgement Requirement

The User agrees to acknowledge the use of the ALPHA research infrastructure in all outputs (including publications, patents, datasets, and reports), including a reference to the infrastructure’s webpage where applicable.

B.10 Acceptance

I confirm that I have read, understood, and agree to comply with the terms and conditions outlined in this User Access Agreement.

Name	
Affiliation / Position	
Signature	
Date	